

Название публикации: «**BLENDED LEARNING APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**»

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Abstract: In general learning any foreign languages except from his mother tongue

takes time and responsibility from students who are trying to assimilate another strange language. In modernizing world for development, the language education system needs to be intensified by means of strengthening self-learning of students. Self-learning, in its turn, can not exist independently; it should be organized and methodically supported by tutors and teaching tools. In this term information technologies that provide online interactive teaching in combination with traditional

class-learning methods can play a significant role. We can call this combination "blended learning".

Key words: blended learning, approach, self-learning, intensify, interactive teaching, place-based learning, online education.

Introduction Due to the public quarantine, schools, colleges, universities and all educational institutions had to switch to online teaching. In this case, the MOODLE system was introduced by the Ministries of Education for teaching in all areas. Using the MOODLE platform that allows to download different-purposed materials including animation and authentic texts for listening and reading and to organize an individual learning circumstance of students monitored constantly by tutors. The capability to get in touch in other languages is becoming an essential part of professional competence of any specialist, no difference what field they work in.

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Main body It's known that Blended learning is an approach in education which combines online educational resources, data and conveniences for online communication at the same time with traditional place-based classroom methods.

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Blended learning, first of all, learners have to adapt to distance learning, be able to control their time and place of study where they can find comfort, sufficient resources and connection with supporters who are teaching. Academic research suggests that blended learning gives learners a more comprehensive understanding of the course content. Because blended learning allows learners to interact with instructors and fellow learners, social learning is supported. Based on the definition by C. Graham, it is divided into three components of blended learning: The first one is face-to-face learning that represents a traditional arrangement which instructors and students meet during classes;

The next one is self-study learning that assumes different types of activities, such as search information on the Internet, web quests, preparation of handouts, e.t.c, performed by students individually. The last one is online collaborative learning – an online cooperative work of students and instructors in forms of webinars, wikis, Skype conferences and so on. It's the fact that current requirements of use of online technologies in study and daily life prompt adult education programs to integrate more technology use to provide opportunities for learners to build technology skills while simultaneously building basic academic skills.

Distance education is defined in NRS Guidelines as follows: Formal learning activity where students and instructors are separated by geography, time, or both for the majority of the instructional period. Distance learning materials are delivered through a variety of media including, but not limited to, print, audio recording, videotape, broadcasts, computer software, web-based programs and other online technology. Teachers support distance learners through communication via mail, telephone, e-mail or online technologies and software.

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If we conclude from the above sources, blended learning, according to the given data, encourages learners by combining the best aspects of in-person teaching with technology-based learning methods. This type of learning foreign languages especially broadens the learners' experience by supporting anytime, anywhere learning, and increases the role of the instructor. It's the best of two training environments—traditional face-to-face classroom training and high-tech learning.

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